

Foundation for Data Governance in 6G

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Abstract—6G networks will require collaborative data ecosystems where information can be exchanged securely, under enforceable usage conditions, and with mechanisms for dynamic consent, cross-organizational policy enforcement, and regulatory compliance. Traditional centralized or siloed governance models—restricted to individual organizations or tightly coupled platforms—are insufficient, as they lack the flexibility, transparency, and interoperability needed for cross-domain, multi-stakeholder collaboration.

We propose a conceptual model for federated data governance tailored to 6G, building on and extending the approaches of Gaia-X and the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA). Gaia-X offers the structural foundation for federation, identity, and trust management, while IDSA contributes mechanisms for usage control, policy enforcement, and standardized data sharing. Based on these foundations, we propose a data governance architecture, embedding interoperability, sovereignty, and trust into the network design through open standards, identity verification, and data contracts.

This architecture aims to ensure that all participants in the 6G data value chain—whether infrastructure providers, application developers, or data owners—can collaborate within a common, enforceable governance framework. This approach lays the groundwork for a trusted, resilient data infrastructure essential to the success of 6G.

Index Terms—Policy, Identity, Data Contracts, Gaia-X, IDSA

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